

INTERNET ADDICTION AND EARLY PORNOGRAPHY CONTACT AS CORRELATES OF ADOLESCENTS' SEXUAL BEHAVIOR: IMPLICATION FOR COUNSELLING INTERVENTION

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Abstract

The study was designed to examine internet addiction and early pornography contact as correlates of adolescents' sexual behavior. The central purpose of this study was to find if there is any significant relationship between early pornography contact and Adolescent's sexual behavior and to ascertain the relative contribution of internet addiction and early pornography contact on adolescents' sexual behavior. Descriptive research design of the correlational type was adopted in which structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The population for this study was all newly admitted 100 level students of Babcock University Nigeria, 2018/2019 academic year. The sample consisted of two hundred (n=200) students; from which 55.5% (n=111) were males and 44.5% (n=89) were female. Data collected were analyzed using Descriptive Statistics (DS), Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA). The finding reveals that there is a significant relationship between internet addiction and adolescent sexual behavior at ($r=.189, P<.05$). More so, the analysis of variance shows a statistically significant composite contribution of internet use among adolescents at ($f_{2,197} = 13.379 < 0.05$). Also, pornography predicts adolescent sexual behavior more significantly than internet addiction. The study stipulates that internet addiction and its significant impact on adolescent's sexual behavior have raised a societal challenge that calls for attention. The need for rehabilitation and support centers in schools and colleges was highlighted, were adolescents traces of internet addiction could receive care and intervention. The need for parents, guardians and teachers to closely monitor the adolescents as they surf the internet was also highlighted.

Key words: internet addiction, early pornography contact, adolescents' sexual behavior

Introduction

Sexual predisposition, transition from virginity to active sexual life, unplanned pregnancy and other negative sexual behaviors prevailing among many adolescents have attracted the interest of researchers in various fields of human endeavors especially in behavioral sciences. Sexual behavior is an act exhibited by individuals to gratify their sexual pleasure (Chawla, &

Sarkar, 2019). Such behavioral displays may portray both biological and cultural influences and involve sexual arousal. Sexual behavior therefore represents an individual's sexual attitude or practice, be it heterosexual or homosexual activities which according to Arulogun, Ogbu, & Dipeolu (2016) are marked by some behavioral changes such as oral sex, body tattoo, multiple sexual partners, homosexuality and lesbianism. Nevertheless, one may not enumerate all the negative outcomes when an individual begins to masturbate for sexual feelings or involves in experimental sexual activity with his or her mates at a tender age. Hugging and squeezing of hands, kissing and torching are also some of the observed sexual behaviors of the adolescents (Maswikwa, Richter, Kaufman, & Nandi, 2015).

According to Aji, Aji, Ifeadike, Emelumadu, Ubajaka, Nwabueze, & Azuike, (2013). Adolescents' sexual behaviors are in the increase in recent times hence sexual curiosity, changes in hormonal secretion and other psychosocial development has also increased, but varies across diverse groups and cultures. These increases of adolescents' sexual behaviors are deviant to some traditional or cultural norms that place considerable importance on morality and also promote sexual relationship only for those in marital union.

Adolescent is derived from the Latin vocabulary "adolescere" which connotes "to grow up" (Mills, 2016). Adolescence is a distinctive and transitional stage of human growth and developmental between childhood and adulthood. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines an adolescent as any person between age 10 and 19. According to (WHO) the group of people who can be regarded as adolescents are people who fall under the age range of 10 and 19. Adolescents therefore, make-up of 16% of the world's population, and in sub-Saharan Africa, 23% of the population are adolescents (UNICEF, 2016). Thus adolescent is a stage of vulnerability and opportunity: vulnerability in the sense of been victims of exploitation, violence and abuses of all kinds that could possibly result to death. And opportunities in the expanse of personal identity, values and developmental growth such that will help the adolescent to navigate through life hazards and vulnerabilities thereby fulfill his or her potential goals. The Internet provides a fundamentally different environment for international marketing and requires a different approach. Now it is unrealistic to apply the same marketing strategies without making some modifications to be appropriate to the electronic edge. This paper touches on the effect of international Internet marketing (IIM)

The Internet in today's hi-tech age has become a more conversant environment for socialization, interaction, communication, and expression that had contributed greatly to the whole development of adolescents mostly in research and studies, self-expression and unabridged socialization. Kwon, Kim, & So, (2020) argued that the most challenging issue with respect to adolescents' internet use is its management and regulation, thus, internet platforms may have some social and unhealthy consequences among adolescents due to rare or no parental and guardian monitoring and private activities. This study observes that good number of adolescents in schools and colleges are hooked to the internet either on their phones, tablets, and iPod or even on their laptop computers, which makes parental or guardian monitory unrealistic, thus they can do whatever thing they like, visit which ever site of their choices and also enjoy some level of freedom and unabridged socialization. According to the World Internet Usage and Population Statistics 2020: 39.3% of Africans, 53.6% of Asians, 87.2% of Latin American and

Caribbean, 94.6% of Northern Americans use the internet. The report gathered by World Internet Usage and Population Statistics 2020 as referenced above shows a rapid internet growth user of 11.559 % in Africa and 5,395 % in Middle East between years 2000-2020. While the percentage of internet users around the world had grown rapidly one may deduce that more than 70% of these users are adolescents, no doubt such obsessive internet use may have negative significant effect on their sexual behavior and total wellbeing. Seyyed-Mohammad-Taghi Ayatollahi (2010) coincided that Internet addiction has negative effect on the behavioral and psychological development of adolescents. Similarly, Smutny, & Sulc (2018) see the internet as a fast-tracker of pornographic materials, hence unwanted pornographic video and pictures may pop-ups as soon as one connects the Internet.

Early pornography contact is an act of watching or been exposed to materials, images, pictures or video clips that are produced to create a sense of erotic arousal at a tender age (Ashraaf & Othman 2019). Pornography distorts an individual's natural thought pattern and behavior about sex and sexuality and also undermines his or her social functioning power (Fagan, 2009), subsequently fair judgment becomes impossible. Therefore this study postulates pornography as the portrayal of any erotic behavior in form of words, arts, pictures, videos or representations that are calculated to stimulate sexual feelings independent of the presence of viewer. Other pornographic representations and sexual activities include: pictures of stripped men and women, masturbation, oral sex, vaginal and anal penetration in an unconcealed manner thus alters both sexual attitudes and behaviors of an individual.

In their view Okafor, Efetobor, & Apeh, (2015) highlighted that internet or cyber pornography is becoming vogue among Nigerian youths. Consequently, good numbers of adolescents are voluntarily or involuntarily becoming victims. They linked the fast growing internet pornography among adolescents in Nigerian to the absence of concrete law against cybercrimes and abuse (Okafor et al., 2015). Little wonder Yamoah & Dei (2015) view Pornography as a catalyst that undermines adolescents' social stability and distorts their natural order of growth and development. Obviously, the Internet has significantly made pornography more easily available and accessible to different group of users especially adolescents (Beyens & Eggermont, 2014).

Adolescents' sexual behavior resulting from early espouse to internet pornography presents a serious global challenge today. Thus the extent to which free accessed internet pornography has negatively affected adolescents' sexual behaviors is alarming. In recent times, observation has shown a growing sexual behavior among adolescents that is characterized by but not limited to display of sexual body parts in public domain, transition from virginity to sexual activities, having multiple sexual partners, pressuring of peers into sexual activities and other socio-emotional problems. Adolescents are more vulnerable to unhealthy sexual activities and their ethical logics about sex and sexuality had become biased at such tender age. If this development is not urgently checked and reversed, it can adversely affect the wellbeing of many adolescents. Therefore, this study was aimed at investigating internet addition and early pornography contact as correlates of adolescents' sexual behavior.

Research Questions

Is there any significant relationship between Internet addiction and Adolescent Sexual Behavior

Is there any significant relationship between Early pornography contact and Adolescent's Sexual behavior

What is the significant composite contribution of Internet addiction and early pornography contact

What is the relative contribution of Internet addiction and Early pornography contact to Adolescent Sexual behavior

Methods

The study employed Descriptive research design of the correlational type. The population for this study was all newly admitted 100 level students of Babcock University Nigeria, 2018/2019 academic year. The sample consisted of two hundred (n=200) students; from which 55.5% (n=111) were males and 44.5% (n=89) were female. All the participants were less than one (1) month in the University community as at the time of study. Data collected were analyzed using Descriptive Statistics (DS) in determining the demographics of the respondents, Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was as also used to answer questions one (1) and two (2) while Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) was used in answering questions three (3) and four (4).

Result and Discussion of Findings

Table1 Demographics of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
		Total= 200	
Gender	Male	111	55.5
	Female	89	44.5

Table 1 shows that the respondents were more of men (111; 55.5%) while the female were (89; 44.5%). This shows that more men participated in the study than female.

Answering Research Question

Research question 1 (RQ1): is there any significant relationship between Internet addiction and Adolescent Sexual Behavior. This questions was tested using Pearson product moment correlation and the result is presented in the table below

Table 2 Summary of Pearson product moment correlation coefficient showing relationship between Internet addiction and Adolescent Sexual Behavior

Variable	Number	Mean	Std. dev.	R	Sig	Remark
Internet addiction	200	28.1150	4.51149	.189	.007	Significant
Adolescent Sexual Behavior	200	14.0550	2.88681			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The result of the analysis reveals that the correlation (r) is at $P < .05$ ($r = .189$, $P < .05$). This means that there is a significant relationship between internet addiction and adolescent sexual behavior. This finding agrees with [Dwulit & Rzymiski](#) (2019) that the Internet was the most often used form of accessing photographic picture and literatures, thus 76.5%, of their respondents admitted browsing online pornography using private or multiple internet modes. The prevalence rate of internet use and its exposure by adolescent has become higher, little wonder the present study found significant relationship between internet addiction and pornographic use among adolescents. However, it is possible that the high prevalence of pornography among adolescent today could be as a result of internet facilities that are available to them without significant restriction, supervision or even guidance. In fact, one may not necessarily desire to log on to pornographic sites before he or she is intimidated by unwanted nude pictures mostly of women. That is to say that the internet presently lures one to see such picture or video clip, in some cases unwanted sex videos are also seen.

Research question 3 (RQ3): is there any significant relationship between early pornography contact and Adolescent's Sexual behavior. This question was tested using Pearson product moment correlation; the table below presents the result.

Table: 3 Summary of Pearson product moment correlation coefficient showing relationship between early pornography contact and Adolescent's Sexual behavior

Variable	Number	Mean	Std. dev.	R	Sig	Remark
internet use among adolescents	200	28.1150	4.51149	.315	.000	Significant
adolescent and internet pornography	200	13.1050	2.49703			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The result of the analysis reveals that the correlation (r) is at $P < .05$ ($r = .315$, $P < .05$). This result indicates a significant relationship between early pornography contact and adolescent sexual behavior. This finding is in agreement with the findings of (Kar, 2015) who found that online pornography addiction had a significantly adverse effect on social and sexual behavior among University students. Also, there are other literatures suggesting that adolescents can learn sexual behaviors from watching the behaviors shown in sexually explicit videos, pictures or other materials (Alexy, Burgess, & Prentky, 2009, Haggström-Nordin et al., 2006). These findings are simply saying that there is a relationship between adolescents' pornography viewing and

sexual behavior. Thus, adolescents' sexual orientation can be negatively impacted by *watching videos and pictures created to arouse sexual interest*. Hence, adolescents tend to imitate what they see because of the peculiarity of their stage in human development.

RESEARCH QUESTION 3 (RQ3): what is the significant composite contribution of Internet addiction and early pornography contact? This question was tested with multiple regressions and the result is presented in the table 4 below.

Table 4 Model summary of the R, R square and adjusted R in the multiple regression analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.346 ^a	.120	.111	4.25459

a. Predictors: (Constant), Pornography And Adolescents Sexual Behavior , Adolescent And Internet Pornography

The correlation coefficient resulting from the multiple regression analysis discloses that there is a moderate correlation ($R = .348$) between the predictors and the criterion variables. The coefficient of determination is relatively mild ($R^2 = .120$) shows a weak strength in predicting adolescent and Internet Pornography. The composite contribution is further interpreted by the ANOVA Summary below.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	484.356	2	242.178	13.379	.000 ^b
	Residual	3565.999	197	18.102		
	Total	4050.355	199			

A. Dependent variable: internet use among adolescents

B. Predictors: (constant), pornography and adolescents sexual behavior , adolescent and internet pornography.

The analysis of variance is very significant ($.000, f_{(2, 197)} = 13.379 < 0.05$). This illustrates that the composite contribution of internet use among adolescents is statistically significant hence it can be assumed that the predictor variables could actually predict adolescents' sexual behavior. This finding indicates that increase in internet usage could also increase adolescent sexual behavior. This finding corroborates (Landry, et. al.2017) that found a statistically significant positive association between high-frequency internet use and increased sexual behaviors over a period of time. This result also predict that when an adolescent watches or observe unusual behaviors there may be some likelihood for such an individual to internalize such behaviors be it normal or abnormal behaviors.

Research Question 4 (RQ4): what is the relative contribution of internet addiction and early pornography contact to adolescent sexual behavior. This question was tested with multiple regressions and the result is presented in the table 4.8.

Table 5 the beta (β) coefficient in the multiple regression analysis showing relative contributions Internet addiction and early pornography contact to Adolescent Sexual behavior contributions

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	17.992	2.037		8.833	.000
Internet Addiction And Early Pornography Contact And Adolescents' Sexual Behavior	.530	.122	.293	4.336	.000
	.226	.106	.145	2.143	.033

From the table 5 above, the (β) weightings of the two predictors' variables are given in the standardized coefficient column, the constant is 17.992 relative to each other, adolescents' sexual behavior and internet pornography has a positive effect on adolescents' internet pornography. ($\beta=.293$) and this is statistically significant ($.000, < 0.05$), pornography and adolescents sexual behavior has a positive effect on adolescent internet pornography. ($\beta=.145$) and this is statistically significant ($0.033, < 0.05$). From the result presented, it can be concluded that both predictor variables had statistically significant effect on adolescent sexual behavior. There different beta values in the result above represent their relative contributions to adolescent sexual behavior. Drouin & Miller (2016), agreed with the findings of the present study, when they noted significant relationships between internet addiction, online erotica use, and online risky sexual behaviors.

Summary of Findings

There is a significant relationship between internet addiction and adolescent sexual behavior

There is a significant relationship between early pornography contact and adolescent sexual behavior.

The composite contribution of internet addiction and early pornography contact among adolescents is statistically significant hence it can be assumed that the predictor variables could actually predict adolescents' sexual behavior

Pornography predicts adolescents' sexual behavior more than internet addiction

Conclusion:

This study has shown evidences that Internet addiction and early pornography contact have significant relationship with adolescents' sexual behavior. Furthermore, the study reveals that due to lack of parental monitoring or insignificant restriction on internet web adolescents are exposed to all forms of online pornographic videos, pictures and materials and some of them have even become addicted to practices shown in those materials.

Recommendations

Treatment and rehabilitation centers are needed in school, colleges, Universities and communities to support adolescents who for one reason or the other are addicted to on line pornography, and as a result their sexual orientation and behaviors are adversely effected

The result of this study has shown that constant use of the internet and early pornographic contact can negatively shape one's sexual attitudes and beliefs. Therefore, the need for close monitoring of adolescents by parents, guardians at home, and teachers at schools and colleges is recommended.

Social activities should be provided to engage adolescents meaningfully and also channel their sexual energy positively; doing that may reduce the time adolescents spend on internet activities.

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